

Ülker Gökberk. *Excavating Memory: Bilge Karasu's Istanbul and Walter Benjamin's Berlin*.
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SELEN ERDOĞAN

Kadir Has Üniversitesi
(zeynepseleenerdogan@gmail.com).

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E*xcavating Memory* by Ülker Gökberk is a distinctive work on Bilge Karasu's *Lağım-laranası ya da Beyoğlu*. The book uses concepts derived from Walter Benjamin's unconventional narratives on his Berlin childhood to reveal what Gökberk calls Karasu's poetics of distortion: the stylistic ways through which Karasu's writing works through his childhood memories and invokes the atmosphere of a bygone multicultural Beyoğlu. The book is strongest in applying Benjaminian concepts to read *Lağım-laranası* and shedding new light on Karasu's inscriptions of alterity and uses of ambiguity as a literary method. Benjamin's definition of "the dialectical image" is central to Gökberk's interpretation of the literary forms Karasu chooses when writing about underrepresented and forgotten minorities living in Beyoğlu in the 1930s.

According to Gökberk, both Benjamin and Karasu avoid giving linear accounts of the past and tend to use memory in a topographical sense, which means that inscription of places like Tiergarten, Sakızağacı, Taksim, and Pera carry distorted, incomplete images of mnemonic traces. By borrowing Benjamin's key concept "the dialectical image," Gökberk explains the function of distortion, disfigurement, and displacement in Karasu's short fragments (p. 21). Dialectical images occur when traces of memory become conscious or, more acutely, through a dialectic interplay between consciousness and trace. It is a snapshot that surfaces the past, appears, and passes momentarily, and is constructed within language. In Gökberk's account, unconventional representations in *Lağım-laranası* are best captured by thinking them in the same modality as that of Benjamin's dialectical images: "[W]riting and reading alterity in Karasu does not result in mimetic reconstruction [of the past]" (p. 37). The story of a long-gone people of Beyoğlu can only be told through distorted traces and the truth "of a bygone moment only in its brief flashing-up in the "now-time" of cognition" (pp. 34-35). To put it differently, in reading Karasu's fragments, Gökberk employs Benjamin's method of representing historical occurrences at the moment of their fading away.

I think the concept of the dialectical image offers a new path for reading Karasu's oeuvre more broadly than only *Lağım-laranası*. The fleeting nature of reality associated with the concept is very much present in the ambiguous and dreamlike construction of many of Karasu's texts. *Lağım-laranası* is different in the sense that Karasu consistently makes use of or plays with the uncertainty of the ethnic and religious identity of the text's narrator and his family. As Gökberk

shows in her close readings of the book's fragments *Beyoğlu Üzerine Bir Metin*, *Bir Söylencedir Beyoğlu* and *Hiç Yoktan Bir Ölüm Daha*, the simultaneous disclosure and covering of minority background work to construct an open-ended, incomplete and incoherent narrative that evades a critical reckoning with the effects of Turkish nationalism. Gökberk reviews the violent events of the 1930s that changed the demographics of Taksim/Beyoğlu/Pera, where Karasu's childhood took place. In doing so, Gökberk shows the significance of Karasu's implicit acknowledgment of non-Muslim minorities' erasure. Through her close reading, however, Gökberk reveals glimpses from Karasu's childhood memories that also confront the difficulties of self-erasure. Vague connections and discontinuous narration serve the purpose of telling an alternative story than the official history and aim to "capture a particular historicity through its ruptures" to use Benjamin's terms (p. 56).

Another important perspective that *Excavating Memory* introduces has to do with Karasu's self-construction as a virtuoso of the Turkish language and literature and as a citizen of the Turkish nation-state who changed his name from Israel to Bilge just before beginning college. According to Gökberk, Karasu is uneasy about his family background and oscillates between hiding and revealing it. Although ethnic difference and homosexuality are the main sources of Karasu's alterity and although both "have been subject to suppression in modern Turkish society" (p. 122), Gökberk argues that "the allusive treatment of ethnic difference [in Karasu's works] indicates a deeper level of repression" (p. 123). Karasu's Jewish background is especially left out of the picture. In reference to Rıfat Bali's research on Turkish Jewry, Gökberk uncovers untold details about Karasu's father and argues that Karasu's father had most likely changed his surname to facilitate his own assimilation. In Gökberk's view, Karasu participates in and expands that erasure by further changing his first name:

[T]hrough the family stories pertaining to his past in Beyoğlu, Karasu's narrator clearly displays an urge to expose the minority identity of his child-subject. Yet, due to both psycho-biographical elements and Karasu's poetics that evades a referential narrative, the inhibition . . . sets in. The psycho-biographical elements are related to Karasu's self-fashioning as a Turkish writer, his self-assimilation into the dominant Turkish culture, and his public silence regarding his ethno-cultural minority background. . . . This context elucidates the conflicted discourse of Karasu's Beyoğlu-narrator, which oscillates between covering and uncovering. (p. 96).

However, Karasu's narrative also demonstrates a confrontation with this erasure. Gökberk stresses several techniques that Karasu uses to create ambiguity, such as putting the selves of the author and the narrator in close proximity in order to guide the reader towards an explication of covered identity. This proximity helps Karasu, Gökberk argues, to find a textual pathway to overcome the inhibition (pp. 100-101). Another example of this dialectic of the exposure and concealment of alterity emerges in the Aunt Marruş figure. Marruş is a nickname that covers the aunt's real name and indicates her non-Muslim identity. The figure entails an ambiguity of ethnic and religious identity, which Gökberk interprets as a dialectical image. That figure is only comprehensible when it displays momentary traces, just like a distorted figure with a diminutive covering the aunt's real name, and therefore her identity (p. 102). The narrator's visit to a Beyoğlu house Aunt Marruş once lived in evokes Karasu's own belonging in Beyoğlu, or his *Beyoğlulu* identity. Gökberk suggests that this sort of remembering, sudden flashes of memory is an encounter with the deepest self, the unconscious (p. 104). Aunt Marruş thus functions as a reminder or a remainder of repressed alterity. As a code for difference, Beyoğlu becomes a mnemonic site where Karasu discovers his origins through enclosing its inscription with a deep opacity (p. 123).

By close reading, Gökberk identifies the fact that the narrator of *Lağımlarınası* treats his matrilineal and patrilineal histories differently. Although neither of his parental heritages is explicitly revealed, Gökberk finds Karasu's paternal Jewish heritage to be almost entirely erased. She explains this absence with reference to Turkish Jewry's tendency to *be quiet* (*kayadez*). According to Gökberk, the narrative carries the quality of a testimony, which demonstrates the climate of silence that characterized the early decades of Turkey's Republican history. Karasu's text "breaks through silence by constructing a Beyoğlu that becomes the cradle of memory, childhood" and also of a selfhood that can recall the differential identity of the milieu (p. 124).

Gökberk draws attention to another indication of the narrator's minority identity: the image of covered mirrors. It is customary for Greek-Orthodox people to cover mirrors during mourning rituals and also for Jewish people during shiva (seven-day mourning) (p. 187). The image of the covered mirror works as an ambiguous symbol that combines the narrator's mixed Jewish and

Rum background. Gökberk suggests that the inscription of such indefinite references to minority customs is very similar to the distorted workings of memory (p. 188). Mnemonic sites such as interiors and passages play a significant role in constructing topographical memory. They work as triggers that start the mnemonic process for remembering alterity.

Finally, I think Gökberk's reading of the narrator's appropriation of his mother's voice plays an important role with regard to the book's central argument. According to Gökberk, the narrative voice in *Lağımlararası* bifurcates to create a stage for the narrator's mother. The narrator merges his perspective with that of his mother and thus internalizes the mother's voice so that an intergenerational pathos can be transmitted. The narrator's strong attachment to maternal family and to his maternal side's disadvantaged, lower-middle-class status translates into a narrative strategy for "regressing to a layer of family history that lies further back than the personal memories from the interwar period," a layer which helps Karasu give voice to "a form of remembering akin to collective memory" (p. 222). According to Gökberk, this allusion to collective experience is also present in the treatment of the figure named Crazy Meryem. Gökberk reads Meryem as a metonym for the collective decline of Pera as Meryem is described as shrinking every single day without dying, belonging to the past and the present simultaneously. With her worn-out clothes, Meryem is among the marginalized of Beyoğlu, an outsider, a defective figure and a remnant of a vanished era. All in all, *Excavating Memory* explains meticulously how *Lağımlararası* is a testimonial to religious and ethnic alterity of the non-Muslim Beyoğlu residents. The book defines Karasu's radical alterity with regard to his family background and it contributes to the theoretical framework of Karasu studies by using concepts that amplify this aspect of his works.